

Enabling Voltage Over-scaling in Multiplierless DSP Architectures via Algorithm-Hardware Co-design

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Abstract—The design of low-power digital signal processing (DSP) architectures have gained a lot of attention due to their use in a variety of smart edge applications and portable devices. Recent efforts have focused on the replacement of power hungry multipliers with various approximation frameworks such as multiplierless architectures that require only a few bit-shifts, additions and/or multiplexers when the multiplicand coefficients are known a-priori. However, most existing multiplierless and approximation-based works have not been combined systematically with voltage over-scaling (VOS) which is considered one of the most effective power saving approaches, while the few that have tried, were applied on specific case studies with custom modifications. In this paper, we are proposing a generic optimization framework that not only minimizes the hardware units in any time-multiplexed directed acyclic graph (TM-DAG) multiplier, but also allows the reliable completion of most operations and the avoidance of random timing errors under VOS. This is achieved by synthesizing alternative coefficients that approximate well the original ones, while also activating shorter critical paths. As a result when VOS is applied, minor quality degradation occurs due to the coefficient approximations which are deterministic by design, while the gained timing slack of the new multiplicands allows us to reduce the supply voltage and circumvent the random timing errors induced by the increased delay under iso-frequency/throughput. Our experiments have indicated that when our framework is applied on fast Fourier transform (FFT) and discrete cosine transform (DCT) architectures, it results in up-to 34.07% power savings, when compared to conventional multiplierless architectures, while it induces minimal signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) degradation, even when voltage is reduced by up-to 20%.

Index Terms—Multiplierless, time-multiplexing, voltage over-scaling, approximate FFT, approximate DCT.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, there is an increasing demand for low-power implementations of various digital signal processing (DSP) and machine learning (ML) algorithms, targeting computation at the edge [1, 2]. In particular, complex algorithms like the fast Fourier transform (FFT) [3–6], the discrete cosine transform (DCT) [7–9], discrete wavelet transform (DWT) [10, 11] and neural networks (NNs) [12, 13] are widely used in many everyday applications like telecommunications [14] and health monitoring [11, 15, 16]. While very insightful and useful, most of the employed DSP/ML frameworks require many arithmetic operations, especially in terms of the multiplications, hindering their use on portable edge devices. To this end, in recent years, the utilization of dedicated low-power processing cores have gained a lot of attention, aiming to significantly reduce the energy consumption by employing

several optimization methods to efficiently perform power hungry operations (e.g. multiplications).

In this context, voltage over-scaling (VOS) is considered one of the most popular power saving techniques [19] for iso throughput. As the supply voltage of a circuit has a quadratic dependence with the dynamic power of a circuit [20, 21], lowering it by a small percentage may result to significant energy savings. However, any reduction under the nominal voltage, entails an increase of the circuit delay, leading to timing failures. In contrast to traditional voltage scaling (VS) or voltage-frequency scaling (VFS) techniques where the clock frequency is reduced along with the supply voltage, trading energy consumption for processing throughput, voltage over-scaling (VOS) focuses solely on reducing the supply voltage while keeping the clock frequency unchanged. This deliberate reduction in voltage results in critical path timing violations, introducing a trade-off between energy consumption and precision of operations. Therefore, it is crucial to control the inaccuracies imposed by voltage reduction, in order to avoid catastrophic failures and rather achieve graceful quality degradation [19–21].

To this end, in the past decades several efforts were proposed to facilitate VOS, while addressing the resultant timing violations [17, 18, 22–32]. A common characteristic of the existing efforts is the addition of extra redundant hardware at the algorithm or architecture/circuit level for detecting and correcting any VOS induced timing violations. Particularly at the algorithm level, the algorithmic noise tolerance (ANT) framework [17, 22–24, 33] proposed the utilization of an approximate circuit, acting as a simplified replica of the main DSP block. This additional circuit could operate correctly under VOS due to shorter but simpler datapaths with some deterministic quality loss. At the architecture/circuit level the use of redundant registers or units were proposed [18, 25, 26] to detect/predict the errors [27, 28] and subsequently modify the clock sampling or voltage settings. Additional techniques include transistor level optimizations [29], selective application of VOS on specific hardware components [30, 32] and the utilization of probabilistic multipliers [31, 32].

However, such schemes come with extra area and timing cost, due to the excess hardware components. Therefore, in an effort to limit the overheads, several researchers have tried to exploit the inherent resilience of DSP algorithms to noise, for addressing any errors. In this context, the significance driven approaches (SDA) have been introduced [7–9, 20, 34–36], which aimed at executing faster, (i.e. with a timing slack) the most important operations, while allowing any error to

Fig. 1: a) Impact of VOS on a DSP combinational block. b) ANT approach [17]. c) RAZOR approach [18].

affect only the less significant parts. Also considering the multiplications, they aimed to simplify them by exploring numerous low-complexity multiplierless frameworks. By doing so the authors achieved additional power savings, while also addressing any VOS induced timing failures. Nevertheless, the SDA methods required application specific changes, like coefficient modifications, which cannot easily be applied on other algorithms, thus lacking a generic solution framework. For instance the approach proposed in [9] required the replacement of multipliers with additions and bit-shifts, whereas also manually modifying the original coefficient set. Meanwhile, any change of the size of the coefficient set or the target DSP algorithm requires careful study and experimentation with several coefficient combinations, which may not be possible and optimal especially for larger multiplicand sets. Therefore, a need arises for a formal reformulation of an optimization problem for the systematic synthesis of proper coefficients that allows to facilitate VOS for multiplierless architectures targeting any DSP algorithm.

In this paper, we are trying to address the shortcomings of existing approaches and aim at proposing an optimized algorithm-architecture co-design framework that can be applied to any DSP multiplicand set that enables VOS. The proposed ERMAC framework (Error Resilient Multiplierless Architecture) synthesizes coefficients that when mapped on a multiplierless architecture leads to adequate timing slacks. This timing gains can contribute to avoid any random timing violation, while only incurring minimum deterministic quality loss. Alongside the VOS facilitation, our approach introduces, for the first time, time-multiplexing which is a popular hardware reutilization technique aiming to achieve further energy savings [37]. ERMAC essentially generalizes existing VOS design methodologies, such as the SDAs, by applying generic optimization heuristics, while avoiding redundant hardware overheads [7–9, 20, 34–36]. The contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Formulate an optimization framework aiming to facilitate VOS via the synthesis of proper coefficients, while minimizing the quality degradation (deterministic and controlled by design), that may incur by the applied approximations and any random timing failures under VOS. The proposed formulation deviates from traditional multiplierless problems [37–43] which focused only on the reduction of resources rather than in the application of VOS, requiring a completely new design philosophy.

- 2) Develop a novel method, named approximate multiplicand search (AMS), that seeks alternative coefficients (for any given set) which can be realized with fewer adders in series, thus having a shorter critical path than the original coefficient set. Also, the proposed search method tries to induce minimum quality degradation helping to maintain acceptable outputs, in case that VOS and approximate coefficients are to be selected.
- 3) Combine the new approximate coefficients, synthesized by the AMS, with the original/exact ones and design multiplierless architectures by employing the minimum number of adders [38, 39, 41] combined with time-multiplexed directed acyclic graphs (TM-DAGs) [37] in a novel way. The designed architectures allow to maintain adequate output quality under VOS by selecting, when needed, the outputs with the shorter datapaths of the approximate coefficients. Note that our approach can generate either single input single output (SISO) or single input dual output (SIDO) time-multiplexed multiplierless architectures like the ones proposed in [4].
- 4) Demonstrate the efficacy of ERMAC on the development of multiplierless architectures for various fast Fourier transform (FFT) and discrete cosine transform (DCT) coefficient sets via post place and route dynamic timing analysis. Our results show that our approach leads up to 34.07% power savings while achieving better signal to noise ratio (SNR) by 28.8 dB than the original, not scalable architecture.

The rest of paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the background and existing VOS methods, while highlighting unaddressed challenges. Section III presents our proposed approach; ERMAC. Section IV highlights the design methodology that we followed to integrate ERMAC with a typical integrated circuit implementation workflow. Section V applies our framework on the design of FFT and DCT architectures. Section VI draws the final conclusions.

II. BACKGROUND-RELEVANT WORKS

This section presents some background and works relevant to the facilitation of VOS on DSP architectures along with some existing challenges that remain unaddressed.

A. Voltage scaling

In several DSP applications, such as FIR filters [35, 44], DCT [7, 9] and FFT [4, 6], there usually exists, a set of

coefficients S as in (1)

$$S = \{c_0, \dots, c_{N-1}\} \mid i = 0, \dots, N - 1, \quad (1)$$

which is essentially a set of N known constants that need to be multiplied with a single input x . An example of such a DSP circuit is illustrated in Fig. 1a. In this case two different timing paths P_1 and P_2 are considered, with path delays $\tau_{P_1} < \tau_{P_2}$ from launch to capture flip flops (FF). So under nominal supply voltage and constant clock period T_{clk} , both paths successfully compute a valid result as $\tau_{P_1} < \tau_{P_2} < T_{clk}$, thus no timing errors occur due to clock period violations.

Conversely, reducing the supply voltage by a small percentage, aiming to achieve quadratic power savings, will increase the delay of the CMOS transistors for all timing paths as shown in (2):

$$\tau_d = \gamma \frac{V_{dd}}{(V_{dd} - V_t)^\alpha}, \quad (2)$$

where τ_d is the switching delay, V_{dd} is the supply voltage, V_t is the transistor threshold voltage and γ, α depend on the physical characteristics of the transistor (e.g. capacitance, transconductance, etc) which are technology and circuit dependent [17, 20]. It is evident that for $V_{dd} > V_t$, as V_{dd} decreases, τ_d will increase thus the supply voltage and the transistor delay are (approximately) inversely proportional. Therefore, as a combinational logic block consists of several CMOS transistors connected in series, lowering the supply voltage will affect the total delay of the timing paths in a cumulative manner. Consequently, any paths with total delay $\sum_i \tau_d(i) > T_{clk}$, violate the clock period T_{clk} of the circuit, leading to timing errors. This property is illustrated in Fig. 1a for P_2 , where the total delay on the combinational logic components violates the clock period ($\tau_{P_2} + slack_{P_2} > T_{clk}$), while P_1 , which has a small delay, will produce a valid result as $\tau_{P_1} + slack_{P_1} < T_{clk}$.

To address the issue of timing violations, it is necessary to increase the clock period T_{clk} of the circuit, while the supply voltage V_{dd} is reduced. This trade-off represents the conventional VS or VFS schemes, which have been the basis of numerous studies (such as [45, 46]) aiming to balance processing throughput with energy consumption while preserving accuracy. In this study, we investigate the effects of voltage over-scaling (VOS), where the clock period (frequency) T_{clk} (f_{clk}) remains fixed, and only the supply voltage V_{dd} is reduced. The objective of VOS is to achieve a trade-off between the accuracy of operations and energy consumption without compromising throughput.

B. Existing VOS-aware works

Focusing on VOS related works, the induced timing failures may lead to significant quality degradation, reducing the achieved SNR of the target application at intolerable levels. To this end, there have been various approaches which can be distinguished in three main categories, that based their error detection/correction mechanisms, aimed to limit the effect of timing errors.

Fig. 2: a) *Normalized DAG for 8032.* (b) *Normalized DAG for 8027.* (c) *Non-normalized DAG for 8027.* (d) *Normalized DAG for 5676.* (e) *Time-multiplexed DAG for normalized 8027 and 5676.*

The first approach, known as ANT [22, 33] is illustrated in Fig. 1b. An ANT based system consists of the main processing unit which computes the exact result, and a replica that approximates the main block. The design challenge of such a system is to derive a replica that sufficiently approximates the original DSP unit, while also having a much smaller critical path. Following the computation blocks, a threshold based comparator determines if the main output meets a certain quality threshold based on the exact and approximate solutions. Thus, after the comparison one of the two outputs is chosen, maintaining the SNR at a tolerable level. Some popular applications based on the ANT framework range from FFT multipliers [17], FIR filters [17, 22] to Viterbi decoders [47] and video processing systems [48]

A second approach is based on the detection/prediction of errors and their correction or avoidance, via proper clock manipulation. The RAZOR-based techniques, introduced in [18, 25], have utilized a shadow latch to double-sample the pipeline stage and a meta-stability tolerant comparator to validate the sampled data, as shown in Fig. 1c. Thus, by replacing the regular FFs, which have the highest estimated timing error probability with Razor FFs, a significant number of timing-errors can be prevented, when VOS is applied, resulting to substantial energy savings. Another similar approach, which is based on elastic clocking, is the so called CRISTA framework [27, 28]. The core idea of this method is to provide the long latency paths (LLPs) an extra clock cycle in order to meet the

required timing constrains. Furthermore, CRISTA insured that the LLPs are rarely activated to minimize the performance penalty of extra clock cycles. Some applications of these VOS approaches are FIR filter design [49], deep neural networks [50], single issue and superscalar processors [18, 51] leading to significant power savings.

While the algorithmic (ANT) and clock sampling manipulation (RAZOR, CRISTA) based methods have proved that significant savings in terms of energy consumption can be achieved, both relied on additional hardware units that try to detect errors and compensate for any quality loss. In an effort to limit such overheads, a third approach called significant driven approach (SDA) have been explored [20], which is based on the inherent error resilience of specific algorithms. The primary goal of this approach is to distinguish the computation of a DSP block in critical and non-critical, and perform the first ones at substantially shorter time to avoid any devastating timing errors, when VOS is applied. Regarding multiplier design, the computation sharing multiplier (CSHM) method have been employed [9], which is a multiplierless framework that constructs intermediate coefficients to achieve some hardware reutilization. Some SDAs were applied on DCT architectures [7–9] color interpolation [34], FIR filters [35] and the DWT [36] based on specific modifications (including coefficient/multiplicand modification).

C. Quality and energy trade-offs

SDA methods have successfully proved that is possible to avoid the overheads of the redundancy based schemes, but they require (substantial) application specific changes, that may need an expert's knowledge and involvement.

To better understand the core principles and conundrums behind SDAs an multiplierless example is illustrated in Fig. 2. Each DAG consists of nodes representing an addition and edges which perform a bit-shift (power of 2 multiplication/division). As shown in Fig. 2b, the multiplicand 8027 can be constructed with 3 adders connected in series, requiring a delay of τ_{P_3} . However, if the original coefficient '8027' is approximated with the very close value of '8032', a datapath of only 2 adders will be activated (shown in Fig. 2a as τ_{P_2}), while inducing a minor error of approximately 0.07%. Evidently, a positive timing slack equal to $\tau_{P_3} - \tau_{P_2}$ (i.e. of one adder delay) could be gained which would suffice to adequately facilitate VOS, while also a substantial part of the computation is guarded.

Moreover, Fig. 3 presents the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) degradation over the supply voltage for the architectures of Fig. 2a. and Fig. 2b. The blue thick line corresponds to the exact multiplication by the original coefficient '8027' (Fig. 2b) while the red dashed line represents the multiplication with the approximate coefficient '8032' (Fig. 2a). As the approximate multiplicand has a positive timing slack of one adder delay $\tau_{P_3} - \tau_{P_2}$ the first point of timing failure (FPF2) occurs at a significant lower voltage level (V_{a_1}) compared with the exact case (V_{e_1}), where three adders are connected in series (FPF1). While there is minor deterministic SNR quality degradation ($S_{a_1} - S_{e_1}$) at nominal supply voltage V_{e_1} due to the induced

Fig. 3: Quality degradation over different voltage levels for the exact and approximate modes of a multiplierless DAG architecture.

timing errors, the achieve accuracy of the exact case rapidly decreases, while the approximate case retains the same SNR until FPF2. Consequently, the effective area of the approximate multiplicand is defined between the voltages of the cross point and the FPF2. Eventually, the maximum gained SNR ($S_{a_1} - S_{e_2}$) is achieved at FPF2, compared with exact case, while the highest voltage reduction is $V_{e_1} - V_{a_1}$.

D. Challenges

Although the preceding approaches seem promising and introduced novel ideas there are some clear design challenges that can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The existing SDA methods [7–9, 34–36] were specifically applied on each case study, requiring manual modifications of the coefficient values. Therefore, a generic formulation must be introduced that can be applied for any given multiplicand set, aiming to adaptively produce architectures that perform significant computations faster, as illustrated in Fig. 2a.
- 2) The produced architecture not only should efficiently map to a VOS-friendly architecture, but also the approximate coefficient must induce the smallest possible deterministic error. This limiting condition is quite difficult to address as the achieved SNR of the approximate multiplicand must be sufficient higher than the SNR of the exact one at FPF2 ($S_{a_1} \gg S_{e_2}$ in Fig. 3)
- 3) Time-multiplexed DAGs, which can drastically reduce the required hardware overhead by reutilizing adder units [37], have not been investigated by the existing SDA approaches. While TM-DAG optimization has been proven to be a NP-complete problem [37], all the existing frameworks have focused on the reduction of the number of units as a way to save power, and did not consider the utilization of gained latency and timing slack facilitate VOS. In addition, utilizing approximate coefficients, alongside the exact ones to construct TM-DAGs, may result in extra area/power overhead due to the excess multiplexers that are required to facilitate both multiplicand sets. Thus, the constructed multiplier microarchitecture must be comprised of minimal hardware resources (adders, multiplexers) while also enabling VOS.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

To address all the challenges mentioned in the previous section we introduce ERMAC. As illustrated in Fig. 6, ERMAC consists of several sub-steps that aim to identify the coefficients that excite the LLPs of the architecture, to search for approximate multiplicands with lower latency and finally construct TM-DAGs with the minimal hardware resources. In the next paragraphs we explain in more detail each step, starting with the reformulation of the problem and its objective function.

A. Objective function

The design of time-multiplexed multiplierless architectures, that facilitate VOS, requires a new problem formulation. The original objective functions, which were introduced in [37–43], have focused on the design of multiplierless architectures by representing the exact coefficients with bit-shifts and additions, neglecting the facilitation of VOS. To this end, as shown in (3) the first objective is to identify all coefficients/multiplicands c_i for set S (as defined in (1)), that have latency (in terms of adder delay) equal to the maximum coefficient latency and replace them with resembling alternative ones (\hat{c}_i) with error $|c_i - \hat{c}_i| \leq er$. After that the exact and the approximate coefficients form the extended coefficient set $S \cup \hat{S}$ that is time-multiplexed using a heuristic that minimizes both the number of adders and multiplexers, while mapping the approximate ones on reduced datapaths.

Given the set $S = \{c_i\} | i \in 0, 1, \dots, N-1$, approx. error er

If $AD(c_i) = \max_AD(S)$

Find \hat{c}_i such that $|c_i - \hat{c}_i| \leq er$ and $AD(\hat{c}_i) < AD(c_i)$

minimize $(\#Adders, \#MUXes)$ of $S \cup \hat{S}$

Where:

$AD =$ Total Adder Delay

$\hat{S} = \{\hat{c}_{a_0}, \hat{c}_{a_1}, \dots, \hat{c}_{a_{L-1}}\} | L \leq N, a_j = \{0, N-1\}$

$\#Adders =$ Number of Adders

$\#MUXes =$ Number of Multiplexers

(3)

B. Approximate Multiplicand Search (AMS)

To estimate the adder latency of a coefficient/multiplicand c_i , all possible DAG representations G_{S_i} have to be evaluated. This is achieved by computing the coefficient tables, provided by the MAG [38, 39] and MAG2 [40] algorithms and traversing the generated DAGs to compute the minimum adder latency of each selected coefficient.

Multiplicand Coefficients										
8022	8023	8024	8025	8026	8027	8028	8029	8030	8031	8032
3	4	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	2
Adder Latency										

Fig. 4: AMS SISO search for $|\hat{c}_i - c_i| \leq 5$ centered at 8027. 8032 is the approximate multiplicand with the best adder latency (2 adders).

Fig. 5: DFS based search algorithm; Each node represents a candidate DAG merging.

To better understand this step, an example is presented in Fig. 4 showing various alternative values of the original coefficient 8027. Similar to the SDA approaches (as discussed in Section II-C) we aim to protect a substantial part of the operation. In particular, we estimate the latency of each coefficient once represented with bit-shifts and additions. According to the MAG [38, 39] algorithm we observe that the coefficient 8027 can be implemented with 3 adders, as shown also in the example on Fig. 2b. Our AMS (Fig. 4) shows that there are other alternative coefficients very close to the original one, $c_i = 8027$, which requires 3 or even 4 adders connected in series. Among the very close alternative coefficients, according to MAG [38, 39], there exist one, i.e., $\hat{c}_i = 8032$, that has an adder latency of 2 (the LLPs traverse 2 adders), as shown in Fig. 2a. Ideally, \hat{c}_i should have the smallest possible multiplication error while having similar graph topology with original DAG. In this case 8032 suffices our conditions and it is selected as an approximation to 8027. Interestingly, as shown in Fig. 2b, the bottom adder computes the coefficient $8027 = 8032 - 5$, therefore we can bypass it to compute the lower latency approximate multiplicand 8032. Note that for dual output SIDO architectures, the AMS search must be performed for both outputs in a 2D plain using the euclidean distance as an error metric (instead of a 1D line for the SISO case, shown in Fig. 4).

C. Architecture mapping

During the mapping step, we have to efficiently time-multiplex the produced DAGs by employing the least number of multiplexers. In addition, we relax the condition of *normalized* DAGs which imposes that one node input should not be bit-shifted [37], by allowing any bit-shift in order to increase the probability of common edge sharing. This is achieved by applying an edge weight transform (EWT) on a *normalized* DAG which basically reallocates a bit-shift for the output edges of a node, to both inputs (or vice versa) as shown in Fig. 2c, for 8027. Consequently, for each *normalized* DAG, that correspond to a coefficient, several *non-normalized* ones are derived which result in high quality TM-DAGs, in terms of the utilized multiplexers.

Following the graph denormalization, the time-multiplexing procedure is conducted. Initially, we perform a node matching followed by a common edge merging check, similarly to the multiplierless method, i.e. DAG FUSION [37]. For example, in case of the the multiplicands 8027 (Fig. 2b) and 5676

Fig. 6: ERMAC and the proposed circuit design methodology.

(Fig. 2d) the optimal node and edge merging is illustrated in Fig. 2e. Furthermore, for our approach instead of using a random permutation based merging heuristic (as in [37]), we have implemented a depth first search (DFS) combined with a threshold metric, which is based on the number of 2-1 multiplexers. As shown in Fig. 5, all possible graph merges can be depicted with a N level connected super-graph, where G_{S_i} are all the DAGs of the coefficient $c_i | i \in 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ (\cup stands for the time-multiplexing operation). Initially we perform a DFS from level 1 to level $N-1$ highlighted as search 1 with the red path in Fig. 5. After that an estimation of the threshold metric is evaluated (in our case the total number of required multiplexers) for the candidate $G_{S_0} \cup \dots \cup G_{S_{N-1}}$ merging. Thus, during the next searches we can truncate all the graph merges (noted as colored \times) at $level < N-1$ that violate the initial estimation of the threshold metric and we continue with the second DFS in order to find a better metric estimation (e.g. a solution that utilizes less multiplexers). So in general an exhaustive search is guaranteed if (4) is met:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{If } best_est = METRIC(\bigcup_{i=0}^{N-1} G_{S_i}) \\
 &\text{Discard all mergings such that:} \\
 &METRIC(\bigcup_{i=0}^k G_{S_i}) \leq best_est \\
 &\text{where } k < N-1 \text{ is the current search level}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Finally, if the admissible TM-DAGs meet the constraints of the required multiplication error er and the number of multiplexers $\#MUXes$, the RTL of the TM-DAGs is produced, written in SystemVerilog. Otherwise if the input constraints are not met we revert back to the AMS step, by picking different approximate coefficients with longer timing paths, and we repeat the whole process again until a sufficient number of the constraints are met, as shown in Fig. 6.

IV. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

In order to evaluate the produced circuits ERMAC is integrated in a typical ASIC design flow, shown in (Fig. 6). To this end in this section we elaborate on the architecture synthesis and evaluation steps of our workflow.

A. Architecture synthesis

After producing the RTL description of the admissible TM-DAGs, we continue with the architecture synthesis (Fig. 6). Initially, we perform a gate-level synthesis, using the 45nm NangateOpenCell library at 1.1V, with Synopsys Design Compiler aiming to achieve the smallest area and latency under the given Synopsys design constraints (SDC). Moreover, the distribution of the timing paths is derived and analyzed to ensure that sufficient timing slack is gained for the approximate coefficients, otherwise the synthesis is repeated until the required specifications are met.

The synthesis step is followed by the place and route (PnR) step using the Innovus tool from Cadence. For our experiments we assumed typical process variations at a voltage of 1.1 V and a temperature of 25 °C. Hence, the actual area and timing is circuit is evaluated by also taking into account the physical characteristics of the design (metal layers, wire capacitance, clock skew, etc.). Sign-off static timing analysis (STA) will follow with Synopsys PrimeTime to verify and resolve any timing violations and finally produce the standard delay format (SDF) file which will be used in the proceeding evaluation phase. Note that for the timing analysis we did not consider pad delay.

B. Evaluation

After obtaining the RTL netlist and the SDF file, which describes the cell and interconnect delays, a post-PnR, gate-level simulation is performed with Modelsim to verify the functionality of our design. Also during this verification step we produce the error-free output results and set up the test-bench for a given DSP application, that will be used in our experiments. Finally, we continue with the dynamic timing analysis (DTA) by selecting various supply voltage levels, thus we can extract the real timing errors that occur due to VOS. To characterize the data-dependent path activation, we use the post place-and-routed gate level simulation supported by Modelsim, which monitors the inputs and the outputs of all the flip-flops of the design. In addition, by generating the value change dump (VCD) file from Modelsim, we can observe the switching activity of the circuit and perform a

power analysis (PA) using Voltus from Cadence, to extract the power consumption of the circuit for various voltage levels.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the efficacy of our approach by applying it on different coefficients sets, shown in Table I, of two popular DSP algorithms; the FFT and the DCT. It is noteworthy that our proposed architectures possess the capability to dynamically perform either all the operations based on the exact coefficients or reduced operations (within shorter delay) based on the approximate coefficients. Regarding the FFT architectures, we have implemented two dual output architectures by employing coefficient sets that were introduced in [4] for W_{16} and W_{32} rotators, which are the main processing elements of pipeline FFT architectures. We present specific results and the proposed microarchitecture for the W_{16} rotator. Furthermore, by employing the rotator transform techniques, as presented in [52], it becomes feasible to construct pipelined FFT architectures of sizes up to $N = 1024$ using only W_{16} and W_{32} rotators. Consequently, we show results for these two rotators, and an in-depth investigation is undertaken to evaluate the impact of VOS in terms of power gains and accuracy of operations per rotator. Concerning the DCT, we have implemented for two sizes; an 1D 8-point DCT multiplier as in [53] and an 1D 16-point DCT multiplier [9], which is widely used in image compression [8, 9]. We present specific results for the 8-point DCT multiplier. Moreover, we summarize the achieved power/energy savings for all the DSP algorithms, operating for a different maximum fixed clock frequency while VOS is induced. Finally, we compare our framework with existing approaches.

A. FFT rotator architectures

The rotator is an essential hardware unit widely employed in pipelined FFT architectures [4, 6]. Essentially, a FFT rotator performs, during a butterfly operation, a complex multiplication on a complex input $z = x + jy$ with a set of constants $c_i = \cos(\frac{2\pi ni}{N})$, $s_i = -\sin(\frac{2\pi ni}{N})$ | $i \in [0, \dots, \frac{N}{2} - 1]$ as in (5).

$$z(c_i + js_i) = (x + jy)(c_i + js_i) = x(c_i + js_i) + y(js_i - c_i) \quad (5)$$

The multiplications $x(c_i + js_i)$ and $y(js_i - c_i)$ can be conducted by a multiplier of one input and two outputs (SIDO). Thus the real part of the output is computed as $c_i x - s_i y$ and the imaginary part as $s_i x + c_i y$, as shown in Fig. 7. Also due to the underlining symmetry over the unit circle, additional input/output multiplexers, that interchange the real and imaginary parts, can be employed to perform rotations over all four quadrants, with minimal hardware overhead. Note that the W_{16}/W_{32} rotators multiply the complex input z with 8/16 different points over the unit circle, while by using their symmetry over the unit circle only 3 and 5 distinct ones are eventually need.

As shown in Table I, we applied our approach for the design of two distinct FFT rotator coefficient sets, noted as *set A* and *set B*, that implement a W_{16} and W_{32} rotator [4], respectively. Following the steps of the proposed approach, discussed in Section III for *set A* FFT coefficients, ERMAC has identified

TABLE I: Multiplicand sets of DCT multipliers and FFT rotators

Set Number	Application	Exact. Coeffs	Approx. Coeffs
Set A	FFT rot. W_{16}	8027, 7416 + j 3072, 5676 + j 5676	8032, 7424 + j 3072, 5632 + j 5632
Set B	FFT rot. W_{32}	209, 205 + j 41, 193 + j 80, 174 + j 116, 148 + j 148	208, 200 + j 40, 200 + j 209, 180 + j 120, 148 + j 209
Set C	DCT-8	512, 473, 362, 196	512, 480, 360, 196
Set D	DCT-16	1024, 1004, 946, 851, 724, 569, 392, 200	1024, 1004, 960, 840, 720, 576, 392, 200

that the coefficients 8027, 7416 and 5676, had the largest adder latency equal to 3, as shown in Fig 8a. Based on that, by applying the proposed AMS, the alternative coefficients 8032, 7424 and 5632, that are close to the original ones, were selected as the best candidates with the lowest error and a reduced latency of 2 adders delay.

Moving on to the next step the DFS-based mapping algorithm merged the DAGs of the approximate coefficients with the DAGs of the original ones returning the architecture shown in Fig. 8b. Note this was possible since our method ensured that the approximate coefficients have similar topology with the original ones, thus facilitating the merging of multiple DAGs under the same architecture, while ensuring maximum resource sharing. The required hardware/power overhead is accounted for only one extra 2-1 output multiplexer and a 3-1 output multiplexer instead of a 2-1 counterpart. Also, the critical path delay remains relatively unchanged as the delay of a 3-1 multiplexer, compared to a 2-1 multiplexer is considered negligible in comparison with the total delay (i.e. 3 adders). Therefore, the developed architecture allows to select the datapath that realizes the approximate coefficients, as highlighted with a red dotted line in Fig. 8b, in case that VOS is applied under iso-frequency/throughput, to take advantage of the shorter delay of two adders and the available timing slack, while also protecting a significant part of the operation.

So, Fig. 9a illustrates the achieved SNR (dB) under different percentage (%) reductions of the supply voltage (in reference with the nominal 1.1 V) for the placed-and-routed 32-bit integer multiplierless architecture of Fig. 8b, which is embedded to a FFT rotator shown in Fig. 7. Our comparison baseline is a full precision floating point FFT rotator. For the evaluation we used as input data a uniform distribution of 50000 19-bit signed numbers (to avoid overflows). It can be observed (Fig. 9a) that when the circuit operates at the exact mode (blue line), under the nominal supply voltage of 1.1V (100%) and $f_{clk} = 200$ MHz, the exact coefficients maintain higher

Fig. 7: Microarchitecture of a complete W_{16}/W_{32} FFT rotator with two SIDO multiplierless cores and I/O multiplexers.

quality in terms of the SNR compared to the approximate ones as expected, due to the applied coefficient approximations. However, under 5% voltage reduction the exact multiplication reveals the FPF, due to the timing violation of the LLPs, while on the other hand the SNR under the approximate mode remains unchanged (57.3 dB). We notice that the approximate mode continues to maintain adequate quality in terms of the SNR for up to 15% voltage reduction, as compared to the exact mode the quality of which drastically falls. Interestingly, the FPF in case of the approximate mode is observed once voltage is reduced by 20% where it still maintains an adequate quality, 28.8 dB higher SNR compared to the quality achieved by the exact mode. Furthermore, we observed that the approximate mode maintains 29.7 dB higher SNR than the exact mode even under 25% voltage reduction. Evidently, for 30% to 50% voltage reduction we notice that the achieved SNR of the approximate mode decreases dramatically as the induced timing violations contribute more to the inaccuracies of the computations. Hence, the effective area (where the SNR remains acceptable) of the approximate mode can be determined from 75% to 95% of V_{dd} .

To provide further insights, Fig. 9b. presents the achieved output error-ratio (%) under various supply voltage percentages (%) for the both modes of the developed circuit shown in Fig. 8b. In either case their references are the outputs of each mode at nominal voltage (i.e. the outputs of the exact or approximate mode under different VOS values is compared with the outputs of the exact or approximate mode at the nominal 1.1V). Under nominal voltage, both modes do not present any timing violations, while the approximate mode is 100% accurate for up-to 15% voltage reduction, due to the positive timing slack that is achieved by the alternative low-latency coefficients. The observed FPF of the exact mode is at 5% voltage reduction (error-ratio = 0.003%) while for the approximate mode it is at 20% (error-ratio = 0.004%). Finally, for 30%, 40% and 50% voltage reduction we observe

Fig. 8: Multiplierless architectures for W_{16} SIDO cores; (a) Exact coefficients of set A (b) Exact/Approximate coefficients of set A.

Fig. 9: SNR measurements on FFT rotators of set A under different supply voltage levels and fixed $f_{clk} = 200$ MHz.

Fig. 10: Average Bit Error Rate (BER) percentage measured on the outputs of FFT architectures of set A under 20% scaled voltage and $f_{clk} = 200$ MHz.

an error-ratio of 4.23%, 15.30% and 32.78% for the exact mode and 0.043%, 0.97% and 8.82% for the approximate mode, respectively.

The dramatic quality loss, especially in case of exact coefficients, under low voltages can be attributed to the massive timing errors that occur per bit position for the exact mode, as illustrated in Fig. 10. In fact we observe that the bit-error-rate (%) (BER), under the exact mode and 20% voltage reduction, of the architecture (presented earlier in Fig. 8b) results in much larger BER compared to the approximate mode operation, where much shorter datapaths are being activated by design. Furthermore it is evident that the highest BER (over than 0.30%) is observed for the 2 most significant bits (MSBs) for bit positions 30 and 31. Note that for BER estimation we performed an extensive DTA on the target post

Fig. 11: DCT compression and reconstruction. The first columnwise 1D DCT is implemented using ERMAC.

Fig. 12: Image outputs of DCT compression in case of exact and approximate mode under various voltage levels; a) Approx. 5% Voltage reduction, b) Exact. 5% Voltage reduction, c) Approx. 20% Voltage reduction, d) Exact. 20% Voltage reduction

Fig. 13: (a) PSNR measurements and (b) Sample Error Ratio under different voltage reduction levels for DCT architecture of set D for $f_{clk} = 180$ MHz

PnR architecture with 50K uniformly distributed 19-bit signed inputs.

Finally, we implemented an entire FFT architecture of size $N = 32$, to measure the achievable power savings when VOS is applied on the employed rotators. Specifically, we have implemented a single delay feedback (SDF-FFT) radix-2 FFT pipelined architecture, which uses 36 complex memory cells (including the pipeline intermediate registers) and three complex multiplierless rotators W_8 , W_{16} and W_{32} , respectively. The latter two rotators are the most power consuming parts of the whole FFT architecture, accounting for the 82.84% of the total power consumption. To this end, when the supply voltage of the last two rotators is reduced by 20% the total power consumption is reduced by 23.90% with minimal quality degradation as the proposed W_{16} and W_{32} rotators can operate on the approximate mode allowing to gain timing slack, thus compensating for timing errors induced by the voltage reduction.

B. DCT architectures

We have applied our ERMAC framework on two different DCT coefficient sets C and D of different sizes, as illustrated in Table I. These sets have been computed according to (6), for $N = 8$, $W = 9$ and $N = 16$, $W = 10$ for, sets C and D respectively, where N is the DCT size and W are the number of approximation bits of (6).

$$c_i = \left\lfloor \cos\left(\frac{i\pi}{N}\right)2^W + \frac{1}{2} \right\rfloor | i \in 0, 1, \dots, N/2 - 1 \quad (6)$$

Considering set D , the exact coefficients 946, 851, 724, 569 require a latency of 4 adders, thus by applying our proposed AMS search, we identified 960, 840, 720, 576, respectively, as the best alternative ones with a reduced latency equal to 3 adder delay. Thus, the resultant architecture, that incorporates both the exact and approximate coefficients, requires 11 2-1 multiplexers, while the exact-only architectures requires only 3 less. Therefore the combined adder and multiplexer area overhead is less than 5%.

In order to test our proposed VOS-friendly coefficient set, we have explored its application on a 1D DCT that can be used for image encoding, as shown in Fig. 11. Specifically, as in [9] we initially separated the input image in 8 by 8 pixel blocks and we performed a 2D DCT by employing two consecutive 1D DCTs; one for each column (where our approach is applied) and one for each row followed by two 1D inverse DCTs (IDCTs) for image reconstruction. Fig. 13a depicts the resulting PSNR (dB) for a decoded gray scale image (Lenna) over various voltage percentages (%) (nominal voltage 1.1V) and a clock frequency of 180 MHz. Each resultant output is compared with the original input image.

For nominal supply voltage the proposed multiplierless architecture, under the approximate mode, yields excellent image quality (67.3 dB) despite the approximations, thus is impossible to be discerned from the original/exact output (over 80 dB). This can be attributed to the low-approximation error of the alternative multiplicands. Moreover, the approximate mode does not have any PSNR degradation and no timing errors for up-to 5% voltage reduction (67.3 dB shown in Fig. 12a), because of the shorter critical paths, while at this voltage level the exact mode leads to 41.1% PSNR reduction (achieves 34.92 dB PSNR as shown in Fig 12b). Furthermore, even under 20% voltage reduction, the approximate mode maintains high quality in terms of PSNR 31.1 dB (Fig 12c) compared the exact one which essentially fails resulting in a drastic reduction of PSNR down to approximately 10 dB that is unacceptable (Fig 12d). Finally, for voltage reduction of 30% and 40% we observe that the achieved PSNR of both modes is reduced to unacceptable levels (< 20.5 dB), thus the effective area is for 95% to 80% voltage levels.

Similar to the FFT architectures, in Fig 13b we have computed the error-ratio of each mode, for several voltage levels, with their operation at nominal voltage. It is clear that the FPF of the approximate mode occurs for voltage at 92.5% due to the gained timing slack, while the exact mode presents an error ratio of 3.68% for 2.5% voltage reduction. Eventually, decreasing the voltage up-to 20%, results in error

TABLE II: Power savings (%) and gained SNR of sets A-D

Set	Freq. (MHz)	95% Voltage		90% Voltage		85% Voltage		80% Voltage		60% Voltage	
		Power saving (%)	SNR gain (dB)								
A	200	9.75	0.1	18.75	1.2	25.66	16.2	34.07	28.8	56.12	5.1
B	176	10.23	5.7	19.43	9.3	26.6	23.3	33.78	24.1	55.61	8.2
C	214	8.82	8.9	17.46	11.6	23.17	12.0	34.15	15.3	53.28	7.8
D	180	11.17	3.6	22.14	12.1	25.32	11.3	30.22	10.6	50.30	8.8

TABLE III: Dynamic energy consumption ($\mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$) for sets A-D

Set	V_{dd} 100%	V_{dd} 95%	V_{dd} 90%	V_{dd} 85%	V_{dd} 80%	V_{dd} 60%
A	21.10	19.04	17.60	16.15	13.5	9.12
B	29.26	26.41	24.41	22.40	20.9	12.6
C	9.95	8.98	8.301	7.621	7.13	4.29
D	37.67	33.99	31.42	28.84	27.0	16.2

ratio of 57.82% and 14.89% for the exact and approximate mode, accordingly.

C. Power measurements

Table II presents the power savings and quality degradation, in terms of the SNR between the exact and approximate mode under various voltage levels and fixed clock frequencies of 200, 176, 214 and 200 MHz for the coefficient *set A* to *D*, respectively. The gained SNR is calculated for the same voltage level, while the saved power is computed by comparing the approximate mode under VOS with the exact mode at nominal voltage. For the experimental evaluation we generated 50000 random inputs on the implemented placed-and-routed 32 bit architectures (as described in Section III-C). We observe that under 5% voltage reduction, the saved power is 9.75%, 10.23%, 8.82%, and 11.17%, while maintaining 0.33%, 10.2%, 12.6%, and 9.2% higher SNR once operating at approximate mode for coefficient *set A* to *D*, respectively. In addition, under more aggressive, 15% voltage reduction, we observe that the saved power is 25.66%, 26.02%, 23.17%, and 25.32%, while maintaining 27.3%, 38.9%, 22.6%, and 11.2% higher SNR once operating at approximate mode, for coefficient *set A* to *D*, respectively. Finally, the maximum power reduction in all cases is observed for 20% voltage reduction which is 34.07%, 33.78%, 32.01%, and 30.01%, while maintaining 56.1%, 47.9%, 11.3%, and 10.1% higher SNR once operating at approximate mode compared to exact mode, for coefficient *set A* to *D*, accordingly.

Furthermore, in Table III we present the dynamic energy consumption, expressed in $E = P(\mu\text{W})/f_{clk}(\text{MHz})$ of the produced circuits of *set A* to *D* for various voltage levels. We can observe that as the clock frequency of the circuits is fixed, reducing the supply voltage V_{dd} will result to lower dynamic power dissipation for iso-frequency/throughput. Specifically, *set D* present the highest nominal dynamic energy at 37.67 $\mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$ which is reduced to 33.99-16.2 $\mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$ for voltage levels 95%-60% respectively. While, *set C* present the lowest nominal dynamic energy at 9.95 $\mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$ which is reduced to 8.98-4.29 $\mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$ for voltage levels 95%-60% respectively.

D. Discussion and comparison with related works

This section presents a qualitative comparison of our proposed FFT and DCT architectures, which facilitate VOS with the existing works introduced in [9, 17]. Furthermore, we conduct

a comparative analysis of our FFT rotator architectures with two VS-based approaches [45, 46], highlighting the differences between these works and our approach. Finally, we elaborate on the effects of process and temperature variations on our proposed architectures.

Considering the ANT-based approach [17], the proposed FFT butterfly block consisted of 4 generic multipliers that performed the required twiddle factor multiplications. While in our approach we have employed resource-efficient SIDO TM-DAGs, as shown in Fig. 7, avoiding any excess hardware. Furthermore, our approach enables VOS facilitation by employing a few additional multiplexers, as shown in Fig. 8b, which account for only $\sim 10\%$ extra area overhead, whereas the replica circuit of the ANT-based approach required $\sim 20\%$ additional area. Regarding an ANT-based DCT multiplier the estimated area overhead can be up-to 36% [9]. Note that as the ANT-based approach is designed at the algorithmic level, thus it can be easily combined with ERMAC which introduces multiplierless architectures at the circuit level. This may lead to higher energy savings and error resiliency, as the ANT approach [17] reduces the power consumption by 58.1% (compared with a conventional generic multiplier-based FFT), while our approach also optimizes the multipliers by employing TM-DAGs that can also facilitate VOS.

Regarding the SDA-based approach [9], the employed multiplier units have not been integrated with intermediate multiplexers to achieve adder reutilization. Thus for a 16-point DCT, a multiplier bank (precomputer) that employed more than 15 adders have been proposed which is used to produce all the required coefficients, whereas in our approach only 4 adders have been used. Finally, comparing our proposed time-multiplexed DCT multiplier with SDA-based one [9], in terms of power consumption, up-to 73.9% power savings could be achieved for similar PSNR. Note that our utilized time-multiplexing and adder minimization algorithms (Section III-A) can be applied on any coefficient set, without requiring manual modifications. Also the substantial energy savings are attributed due to the fact that your architecture not only requires significantly less hardware components, as consequence of the utilization of minimum adder graphs [38–40] and multiplexers, but also supports aggressive VOS for further energy reduction.

Additionally, in both studies [45] and [46], a VS-based FFT design approach have been adopted by reducing both the supply voltage and the clock frequency, while the throughput is maintained by using super-pipelining and dynamically adaptable pipelines, respectively. In our approach, we take a different route by focusing, for the first time, on multiplierless implementations for the FFT rotators alongside with VOS, without changing the clock frequency. Furthermore, our

approach aims at modifying the coefficients (algorithm) such that they provide timing slack that is used to address any delay increase due to VOS., while maintaining the same target clock frequency/throughput (as opposed to [45, 46].)

Furthermore, the delay of a circuit is significantly impacted by temperature and process variations [20, 45]. Process variations introduce deviations in circuit performance due to factors such as impurity concentrations, oxide thicknesses, and non-uniform process parameters like varying transistor lengths, which directly affect the critical path delay. Additionally, temperature variations reduce electron and hole mobility, further increasing propagation delay. The proposed framework, ERMAC, provides timing slack, which can be utilized to mitigate the delay increase induced either by voltage overscaling (VOS) (as our primary target) or by process/temperature variations. To investigate the impact of these variations, we conducted experiments under an isochronous clock frequency of 200 MHz on the design of the *set A* FFT rotator. We specifically examined slow-slow (SS) and fast-fast (FF) corner cases and compared the results with the typical-typical (TT) counterparts.

Under the nominal voltage of 1.1 V, the FF case, for both the exact and approximate modes, did not exhibit any SNR reduction compared to the TT case, as the FF case operates at 0 °C with fewer process variations, resulting in an increased timing slack of 7%. Therefore, if VOS is applied to the FF cases, the FPFs for both modes (shown in Fig. 9a) appear at 92% and 77% of the nominal supply voltage (1.1 V) for the exact and approximate mode, respectively. On the other hand, in the SS case where the circuit operates at 125 °C with more process variations compared to the TT case, the exact mode exhibits timing failures, dramatically reducing the SNR to below 55 dB. In contrast despite the SS corner case conditions, the approximate mode, benefiting from the gained timing slack due to the shorter LLPs, successfully computes all operations, inducing only the *a-priori* known approximation error.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a new optimization framework named ERMAC, that enables the facilitation of voltage over-scaling on time-multiplexed multiplierless architectures, for achieving aggressive power savings. Our approach is based, on the identification of coefficients that activate the LLPs, and the synthesis of alternative approximate ones with lower latency. By doing so the proposed approach implements, for the first time, adaptive time-multiplexed multiplierless architectures that can maintain adequate quality even under VOS and avoid timing violations for a large voltage range. Our experimental results show that when ERMAC is applied on the design of FFT rotator architectures it results in up-to 34.07% power savings, when compared to conventional multiplierless architectures, while it incurs minor SNR degradation, even when voltage is reduced by 20%. Finally, we have tested ERMAC on DCT based image compression, resulting in nearly 10 dB higher PSNR than the non-scaled architecture, for voltage reduction of 20%.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Martin Wisniewski, J.-M. Bec, G. Boguszewski, and A. Gamatié, “Hardware Solutions for Low-Power Smart Edge Computing,” *J. Low Power Electron. Appl.*, vol. 12, no. 4, 2022.
- [2] L. Kong, J. Tan, J. Huang, G. Chen, S. Wang, X. Jin, P. Zeng, M. Khan, and S. K. Das, “Edge-Computing-Driven Internet of Things: A survey,” *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 55, no. 8, Dec 2022.
- [3] J. W. Cooley and J. W. Tukey, “An algorithm for the machine calculation of complex Fourier series,” *Math. of Comput.*, vol. 19, pp. 297–301, 1965.
- [4] M. Garrido, F. Qureshi, and O. Gustafsson, “Low-Complexity Multiplierless Constant Rotators Based on Combined Coefficient Selection and Shift-and-Add Implementation (CCSSI),” *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 2002–2012, 2014.
- [5] S. S. G. Kumar and P. Meher, “50 years of FFT algorithms and applications,” *Circuits Syst. Signal Process.*, vol. 38, no. 12, pp. 5665–5698, 2019.
- [6] C. Eleftheriadis and G. Karakonstantis, “Energy-Efficient Fast Fourier Transform for Real-Valued Applications,” *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. II*, vol. 69, no. 5, pp. 2458–2462, 2022.
- [7] N. Banerjee, G. Karakonstantis, and K. Roy, “Process Variation Tolerant Low Power DCT Architecture,” in *IEEE DATE.*, 2007, pp. 1–6.
- [8] G. Karakonstantis, D. Mohapatra, and K. Roy, “System level DSP synthesis using voltage overscaling, unequal error protection & adaptive quality tuning,” in *IEEE SIPS.*, 2009, pp. 133–138.
- [9] G. Karakonstantis, N. Banerjee, and K. Roy, “Process-Variation Resilient and Voltage-Scalable DCT Architecture for Robust Low-Power Computing,” *IEEE Trans. VLSI Syst.*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 1461–1470, 2010.
- [10] H. Guo and C. Burrus, “Wavelet transform based fast approximate Fourier transform,” in *IEEE ICASSP.*, vol. 3, 1997, pp. 1973–1976 vol.3.
- [11] G. Karakonstantis, A. Sankaranarayanan, M. M. Sabry, D. Atienza, and A. Burg, “A quality-scalable and energy-efficient approach for spectral analysis of heart rate variability,” in *IEEE DATE.*, 2014, pp. 1–6.
- [12] S. S. Sarwar, S. Venkataramani, A. Raghunathan, and K. Roy, “Multiplier-less Artificial Neurons exploiting error resiliency for energy-efficient neural computing,” in *IEEE DATE.*, 2016, pp. 145–150.
- [13] H. Fan, T. Chau, S. I. Venieris, R. Lee, A. Kouris, W. Luk, N. D. Lane, and M. S. Abdelfattah, “Adaptable Butterfly Accelerator for Attention-based NNs via Hardware and Algorithm Co-design,” in *IEEE/ACM MICRO.*, oct 2022, pp. 599–615.
- [14] S. Queiroz, J. P. Vilela, and E. Monteiro, “Is FFT Fast Enough for Beyond 5G Communications? A Throughput-Complexity Analysis for OFDM Signals,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 104 436–104 448, 2022.
- [15] M. Estévez, C. Machado, G. Leisman, T. Estévez-Hernández, A. Arias-Morales, A. Machado, and

- J. Montes-Brown, "Spectral analysis of heart rate variability," *Int. J. Disabil. Human*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 5–17, 2016.
- [16] C. Eleftheriadis and G. Karakonstantis, "Fast and Accurate Power Spectral Analysis of Heart Rate Variability using Fast Gaussian Gridding," in *IEEE CinC.*, vol. 48, 2021, pp. 1–4.
- [17] B. Shim, S. Sridhara, and N. Shanbhag, "Reliable low-power digital signal processing via reduced precision redundancy," *IEEE Trans. VLSI Syst.*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 497–510, 2004.
- [18] D. Ernst, S. Das, S. Lee, D. Blaauw, T. Austin, T. Mudge, N. S. Kim, and K. Flautner, "Razor: circuit-level correction of timing errors for low-power operation," *IEEE/ACM MICRO.*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 10–20, 2004.
- [19] J. Han and M. Orshansky, "Approximate computing: An emerging paradigm for energy-efficient design," in *IEEE ETS*, 2013, pp. 1–6.
- [20] G. Karakonstantis, A. Chatterjee, and K. Roy, "Containing the Nanometer "Pandora-Box": Cross-Layer Design Techniques for Variation Aware Low Power Systems," *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 19–29, 2011.
- [21] B. Moons and M. Verhelst, "DVAS: Dynamic Voltage Accuracy Scaling for increased energy-efficiency in approximate computing," in *IEEE/ACM ISLPED.*, 2015, pp. 237–242.
- [22] R. Hegde and N. Shanbhag, "Soft digital signal processing," *IEEE Trans. VLSI Syst.*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 813–823, 2001.
- [23] B. Shim, N. Shanbhag, and S. Lee, "Energy-efficient soft error-tolerant digital signal processing," in *IEEE ACSSC.*, vol. 2, 2003, pp. 1493–1497 Vol.2.
- [24] G. V. Varatkar and N. R. Shanbhag, "Energy-efficient motion estimation using Error-Tolerance," in *IEEE/ACM ISLPED.*, 2006, pp. 113–118.
- [25] C. Das, C. Tokunaga, S. Pant, and W. Ma, "RazorII: In situ error detection and correction for PVT and SER tolerance," *IEEE/ACM MICRO.*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 32–48, Jan. 2009.
- [26] R. G. Rizzo and A. Calimera, "Implementing Adaptive Voltage Over-Scaling: Algorithmic Noise Tolerance vs. Approximate Error Detection," *J. Low Power Electron. Appl.*, vol. 9, 2019.
- [27] S. Ghosh, S. Bhunia, and K. Roy, "CRISTA: A New Paradigm for Low-Power, Variation-Tolerant, and Adaptive Circuit Synthesis Using Critical Path Isolation," *IEEE Trans. Comput.-Aided Design Integr. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 1947–1956, 2007.
- [28] D. Mohapatra, G. Karakonstantis, and K. Roy, "Low-power process-variation tolerant arithmetic units using input-based elastic clocking," in *IEEE/ACM ISLPED.*, 2007, pp. 74–79.
- [29] A. Sadeghi, N. Shiri, M. Rafiee, A. Darabi, and E. Abiri, "Voltage over-scaling CNT-based 8-bit multiplier by high-efficient GDI-based counters," *IET Computers & Digital Techniques*, November 2022.
- [30] H. Afzali-Kusha, M. Vaeztourshizi, M. Kamal, and M. Pedram, "Design Exploration of Energy-Efficient Accuracy-Configurable Dadda Multipliers with improved Lifetime Based on Voltage Overscaling," *IEEE Trans. VLSI Syst.*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 1207–1220, 2020.
- [31] M. S. Lau, K.-V. Ling, and Y.-C. Chu, "Energy-Aware Probabilistic Multiplier: Design and Analysis," in *CASES*, 2009, p. 281–290.
- [32] A. Gupta, S. Mandavalli, V. J. Mooney, K.-V. Ling, A. Basu, H. Johan, and B. Tandinus, "Low Power Probabilistic Floating Point Multiplier Design," in *IEEE Computer Society Annual Symposium on VLSI*, 2011, pp. 182–187.
- [33] R. Hegde and N. Shanbhag, "Energy-efficient signal processing via algorithmic noise-tolerance," in *IEEE/ACM ISLPED.*, 1999, pp. 30–35.
- [34] N. Banerjee, G. Karakonstantis, J. H. Choi, C. Chakrabarti, and K. Roy, "Design Methodology for Low Power and Parametric Robustness Through Output-Quality Modulation: Application to Color-Interpolation Filtering," *IEEE Trans. Comput.-Aided Design Integr. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 1127–1137, 2009.
- [35] J. H. Choi, N. Banerjee, and K. Roy, "Variation-Aware Low-Power Synthesis Methodology for Fixed-Point FIR Filters," *IEEE Trans. Comput.-Aided Design Integr. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 87–97, 2009.
- [36] V. Gupta, G. Karakonstantis, D. Mohapatra, and K. Roy, "VEDA: Variation-aware energy-efficient Discrete Wavelet Transform architecture," in *IEEE ICCD.*, 2010, pp. 260–265.
- [37] P. Tummeltshammer, J. C. Hoe, and M. Puschel, "Time-Multiplexed Multiple-Constant Multiplication," *IEEE TCAD*, vol. 26, no. 9, 2007.
- [38] A. Dempster and M. Macleod, "Multiplication by an integer using minimum adders," in *IEE Coll. on Mathematical Aspects of DSP*, 1994, pp. 11/1–11/4.
- [39] O. Gustafsson, A. Dempster, and L. Wanhammar, "Extended results for minimum-adder constant integer multipliers," in *IEEE ISCAS.*, vol. 1, 2002, pp. I–I.
- [40] A. Dempster and M. Macleod, "Multiplication by two integers using the minimum number of adders," in *IEEE ISCAS.*, 2005, pp. 1814–1817 Vol. 2.
- [41] S. Demirsoy, I. Kale, and A. Dempster, "Synthesis of reconfigurable multiplier blocks: part - II algorithm," in *IEEE ISCAS.*, 2005, pp. 540–543 Vol. 1.
- [42] S. Demirsoy and I. Kale, "Reconfigurable Multiplier Blocks: Structures, Algorithm and Applications," *CSSP*, vol. 26, pp. 793–827, 2007.
- [43] M. Faust, O. Gustafsson, and C.-H. Chang, "Reconfigurable multiple constant multiplication using minimum adder depth," in *ASILOMAR*, 2010, pp. 1297–1301.
- [44] S. Demirsoy, I. Kale, and A. Dempster, "Efficient implementation of digital filters using novel reconfigurable multiplier blocks," in *ASILOMAR*, vol. 1, 2004, pp. 461–464 Vol.1.
- [45] D. Jeon, M. Seok, C. Chakrabarti, D. Blaauw, and D. Sylvester, "A super-pipelined energy efficient sub-threshold 240 ms/s fft core in 65 nm cmos," *IEEE J*

- Solid-State Circuits.*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 23–34, 2012.
- [46] S. Jain, L. Lin, and M. Alioto, “Dynamically adaptable pipeline for energy-efficient microarchitectures under wide voltage scaling,” *IEEE J Solid-State Circuits.*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 632–641, 2018.
- [47] R. A. Abdallah and N. R. Shanbhag, “Error-Resilient Low-Power Viterbi Decoder Architectures,” *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 4906–4917, 2009.
- [48] G. V. Varatkar and N. R. Shanbhag, “Error-Resilient Motion Estimation Architecture,” *IEEE/ACM ISLPED.*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1399–1412, 2008.
- [49] V. P. Krishnammal and V. Vijayakumari, “Timing error performance analysis for low power DSP filters,” in *IEEE I-SMAC*, 2017, pp. 811–815.
- [50] D. Ji, D. Shin, and J. Park, “An Error Compensation Technique for Low-Voltage DNN accelerators,” *IEEE Trans. VLSI Syst.*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 397–408, 2021.
- [51] P. Ndai, N. Rafique, M. Thottethodi, S. Ghosh, S. Bhunia, and K. Roy, “Trifecta: A Nonspeculative Scheme to Exploit Common, Data-Dependent Subcritical Paths,” *IEEE Trans. VLSI Syst.*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. 53–65, jan 2010.
- [52] R. Andersson and M. Garrido, “Using Rotator Transformations to Simplify FFT Hardware Architectures,” *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I*, vol. 67, no. 12, pp. 4784–4793, 2020.
- [53] S. Demirsoy, A. Dempster, and I. Kale, “Design guidelines for reconfigurable multiplier blocks,” in *IEEE IS-CAS.*, vol. 4, 2003, pp. IV–IV.

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